

Assessment of FGF-23 level and relationship with PTH and biochemical markers in patients with CKD undergoing hemodialysis

Evaluación del nivel de FGF-23 y relación con PTH y marcadores bioquímicos en pacientes con ERC en hemodiálisis

Noor Ahmed Mohammed noo21s3002@uoanbar.edu.iq <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8997-6254> Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Anbar, Ramadi, Iraq

Hameed Hussein Ali¹ Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Anbar, Ramadi, Iraq sc.dr.hameedh.ali@uoanbar.edu.iq <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9735-1530>

Amer Jihad Hussein dramerjihad68@yahoo.com <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7973-8447> Department of Medicine, Al-Ramadi Teaching Hospital, Ramadi, Anbar, Iraq

Received: 11/20/2022 Accepted: 02/19/2023 Published: 03/12/2024 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10870074>

78

Abstract

Background /Aims: In chronic renal disease, fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23) is a phosphaturic factor mainly produced from bone and crucial for maintaining mineral balance. However, the connection between FGF23 and mineral balance in chronic hemodialysis (CHD) patients remains unknown. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the relationship between FGF-23 and electrolyte variables, such as phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), and chloride (Cl⁻), as well as parathyroid hormone in CKD patients receiving hemodialysis.

Methods: The study included 50 control groups, 60 patients with end-stage renal disease undergoing hemodialysis in the dialysis center at Al-Ramadi Teaching Hospital, Al-Anbar, Iraq. They were aged 20 years or over. FGF23, PTH, P, Ca, Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, Creatinine, and Urea were measured in both patients and the control group.

Results: This study demonstrated a substantial increase in the mean concentration rate of FGF23 (335.34±132.09 pg/mL) in patients compared to the mean concentration rate in the control group (78.20±40.96 pg/mL). Additionally, the study showed a significant increase in the concentration of creatinine, urea, PTH, P, and K⁺, while a significant decrease was observed in the concentration of Na⁺ in patients. However, the study found no significant difference in Ca and Cl⁻ levels between patients and the control group.

Conclusion: The results showed that FGF23 significantly correlates with creatinine, urea, PTH, phosphorus, and calcium. However, our study did not find any statistically significant correlation to indicate an impact of FGF23 on parameters like Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease (CKD), Hemodialysis (HD), Fibroblast growth factor-23 (FGF-23), Parathyroid hormone (PTH)

Resumen

Antecedentes/Objetivos: En la enfermedad renal crónica, el factor de crecimiento de fibroblastos 23 (FGF23) es un factor fosfatúrico producido principalmente a partir del hueso y crucial para mantener el equilibrio mineral. Sin embargo, aún se desconoce la conexión entre FGF23 y el equilibrio mineral en pacientes en hemodiálisis crónica (CHD). Por lo tanto, este estudio tiene como objetivo investigar la relación entre el FGF-23 y variables electrolíticas, como fósforo (P), calcio (Ca), sodio (Na⁺), potasio (K⁺) y cloruro (Cl⁻), así como la hormona paratiroidea en pacientes con ERC que reciben hemodiálisis.

Métodos: El estudio incluyó 50 grupos de control, 60 pacientes con enfermedad renal terminal sometidos a hemodiálisis en el centro de diálisis del Hospital Universitario Al-Ramadi, Al-Anbar, Irak. Tenían 20 años o más. Se midieron FGF23, PTH, P, Ca, Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, Creatinina y Urea tanto en los pacientes como en el grupo control.

Resultados: Este estudio demostró un aumento sustancial en la tasa de concentración media de FGF23 (335,34±132,09 pg/mL) en pacientes en comparación con la tasa de concentración media en el grupo de control (78,20±40,96 pg/mL). Además, el estudio demostró se observó un aumento significativo en la concentración de creatinina, urea, PTH, P y K⁺, mientras que se observó una disminución significativa en la concentración de Na⁺ en los pacientes. Sin embargo, el estudio no encontró diferencias significativas en los niveles de Ca y Cl⁻ entre los pacientes y el grupo de control.

Conclusión: Los resultados mostraron que FGF23 se correlaciona significativamente con creatinina, urea, PTH, fósforo y calcio. Sin embargo, nuestro estudio no encontró ninguna correlación estadísticamente significativa que indique un impacto del FGF23 en parámetros como Na⁺, K⁺ y Cl⁻.

Palabras clave: Enfermedad renal crónica (ERC), Hemodiálisis (HD), Factor de crecimiento de fibroblastos-23 (FGF-23), Hormona paratiroidea (PTH)

In chronic kidney disease (CKD), circulating FGF23 levels progressively increase with decreasing kidney function. However, the increase in FGF23 is most definite in patients with advanced CKD¹. The increase in FGF23 begins early in CKD as a physiological response to reduce serum phosphate levels with decreasing intact nephrons². When the glomerular filtration rate (GFR), drops to (20-30) mL/min/1.73 m², the concentration of FGF-23 in the body increases by five times. In stage five of renal failure, when GFR is less than 15 mL/min/1.73 m², the concentration of FGF-23 in the body reaches levels 800 times greater than the reference value (>59,000 RU/mL). This increase in concentration mainly occurs in bone, and the primary circulating form is known as iFGF-23³.

FGF-23 is a 251-amino acid protein that is synthesized by osteocytes and osteoblasts and secreted into the circulation after cleavage of a 24-amino acid leader sequence⁴. It has a molecular weight of 30 kDa and is found on chromosome 12p13 in humans⁵, its physiological functions are P, Ca, Na⁺, and vitamin D homeostasis⁶. The FGF-23 protein consists of two domains, N-terminal and C-terminal. These domains are separated by a region that includes a cleavage site, for enzymes called endoproteases⁷. The N-terminal domain of FGF23 interacts with the FGF receptor (FGFR), whereas the C-terminal domain interacts with its co-receptor, α -Klotho (α KL)⁸. FGF23 activates the FGFR in the presence of the obligate co-receptor α KL, and the parathyroid gland expresses both FGFRs and α KL⁹.

Secondary hyperparathyroidism is an encountered issue in kidney disease caused by low calcium, high phosphorus, and insufficient vitamin D levels. PTH levels are usually accompanied by elevated FGF23 levels¹⁰. It is commonly believed that there is a feedback loop, between FGF23 and PTH where PTH stimulates the production of FGF23 and in response, FGF23 suppresses the synthesis of PTH¹¹. Studies conducted on rats have revealed that an increase in the transcription of FGF23 due to high dietary phosphate levels is only possible when the serum calcium levels are also high. Another study demonstrated that high phosphate levels do not lead to increased FGF23 transcription but rather the development of calciprotein particles (CCPs)¹². CCPs are calcium and phosphate nanoparticles in the blood that contribute to vascular calcification. When UMR106 cells were treated with synthesized CCPs, increased FGF23 mRNA¹².

The study included fifty healthy controls (25 males and 25 females) aged 20–86 years and sixty patients (35 males and 25 females) aged 20–85 years with CKD undergoing hemodialysis in the dialysis center at Al-Ramadi Teaching Hospital, Al-Anbar, Iraq. All patients with documented end-stage renal disease on hemodialysis (HD). They were on the regular HD program around 2-3 times per week (ie., 8–12 hours). The duration of their hemodialysis varied between a minimum of one month and a maximum of five years. Patients were excluded from the study with malignancy and signs of infection or the hepatitis B or C virus.

Measurement of biochemical markers

About five mL of venous blood sample was drawn from all the subjects; (control and patients) blood was poured into a gel tube to obtain serum by centrifugation at room temperature (18–25 °C) at 3500 rpm for 15 min. After being separated into different parts using Eppendorf tubes, the samples were stored at -20°C until biochemical analysis. The following parameters were measured using commercial kits from Roche, Switzerland. creatinine, urea, phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), chloride (Cl⁻), and Cobas C 311 analyzers were utilized to conduct the analysis. While serum levels of parathyroid hormone (PTH) were automatically measured using the Cobas e 411 analyzer from Roch, fibroblast growth factor-23 (FGF-23) levels were measured using an ELISA kit from ELK Biotechnology Company, China.

Statistical analysis

All analyses were conducted by SPSS-28. The data was presented using simple measures of mean and standard deviation (SD). The significance of differences between different means was tested using the student t-test for differences between two independent means. Statistical significance was considered whenever the P-value was equal to or less than 0.05. Pearson correlation coefficients were utilized to examine bivariate associations.

In Table 1, The individuals' standard experimental features are shown. The eGFR levels (mL/min) of the HD patients were significantly lower than those of the control group (9.11 vs 108.64), with a p-value of 0.0001. Additionally, the serum levels of creatinine and urea were significantly higher in the HD patients than in the control group (6.72 vs 0.71) and (136.23 vs 32.22), respectively. The study revealed a significant increase in serum levels of FGF23 (pg/mL), PTH (pg/mL), P (mg/dL), and K⁺ (mmol/L) in HD patients compared to the control group (p < 0.05). (335.34 vs 78.20), (229.73 vs 50.47), (5.98 vs 3.55), and (4.47 vs 4.22) respectively. There was a significant decrease (p= 0.0001) in serum levels Na⁺ (mmol/L) (128.44 vs 136.97).

Table 1: Mean ± SD for the measured variables in patients and control group

Variable	Control group Mean±SD	Patients group Mean±SD	P-Value
Age (years)	48.6±17.5	52.1±16.5	0.287
BMI (Kg/m ²)	26.4±2.6	27.3±4.4	0.214
eGFR (mL/min)	108.64±17.68	9.11±3.18	0.0001#
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.71±0.11	6.72±2.02	0.0001#
Urea (mg/dL)	32.22±8.66	136.23±49.52	0.0001#
FGF23 (pg/mL)	78.20±40.96	335.34±132.09	0.0001#
PTH (pg/mL)	50.47±19.71	229.73±156.13	0.0001#
P (mg/dL)	3.55±0.60	5.98±1.87	0.0001#
Ca (mg/dL)	8.74±0.43	9.02±0.79	0.057
Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	136.97±3.26	128.44±3.46	0.0001#
K ⁺ (mmol/L)	4.22±0.33	4.47±1.01	0.012#
Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)	100.87±1.91	100.28±4.82	0.271

#Significant difference between two independent means using Students-t-test at 0.05 level.

Table 2: The Correlation between FGF23 and studied variables in patients and control group

Variable	r (FGF23 pg/mL)	P-Value
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.595**	<0.0001
Urea (mg/dL)	0.563**	<0.0001
PTH (pg/mL)	0.415*	0.016
P (mg/dL)	0.368*	0.05
Ca (mg/dL)	0.233*	0.014
Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	0.178	0.061
K ⁺ (mmol/L)	0.056	0.555
Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)	-0.014	0.881

*Correlation is significant at p-value 0.05.

**Correlation is significant at p-value 0.01

The results of this study show a strong positive correlation of FGF23 with creatinine, and urea (p-value <0.0001) as shown in (Table 2) and (Figures 1-2). While non-significant correlations were between FGF23 with Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻. In addition, a positive correlation of FGF23 was observed with PTH, P, and Ca (p-value <0.05).

Figure 1. Correlation between FGF23 with Creatinine

Figure 2. Correlation between FGF23 with urea

Figure 3. Correlation between FGF23 with PTH

Figure 4. Correlation between FGF23 with P

Figure 5. Correlation between FGF23 with Ca

Figure 6. Correlation between FGF23 with Na⁺

Figure 7. Correlation between FGF23 with K⁺

Figure 8. Correlation between FGF23 with Cl⁻

Discussion

The kidneys' primary function is to regulate water, electrolytes, mineral ions, and eliminate metabolic waste. However, without proper treatment, a majority of CKD patients progress to permanent renal failure, which disrupts the body's water, electrolytes, and mineral ions balance. Studies revealed that CKD patients have significantly elevated levels of FGF23 in their bloodstream, which can be attributed to the impaired renal clearance of FGF23¹³. In this study, FGF23 levels were significantly elevated in patients compared to apparently healthy controls. Our findings are in agreement with another study¹⁴. The higher levels of serum FGF23 in CKD may be due to hyperphosphatemia, a novel molecule that stimulates FGF23 secretion, or low Klotho expression states as in Klotho deficiency¹⁵. Blood phosphate levels drop due to FGF23 binding to its co-receptor α-Klotho and FGF receptors in the kidney preventing 1,25D synthesis¹⁶. Our findings agree with other studies that have found elevated FGF23 levels in HD patients¹⁷.

CKD can result in impaired renal vitamin D synthesis. PTH plays a major role in activating the enzyme 1-α-hydroxylase for the hydroxylation of 25-hydroxy vitamin D to 1,25-hydroxy vitamin D. Over time, vitamin D deficiency can lead to reduced gastrointestinal absorption of calcium, positive feedback to the parathyroid glands, parathyroid hyperplasia, and secondary hyperparathyroidism. In late-stage CKD, PTH may be unable to ensure renal phosphate excretion, which can cause hypocalcemia, hyperphosphatemia, and low vitamin D levels, as well as other negative effects. Therefore, calcium and vitamin D supplementation, and phosphate binders, are usually initiated in late-stage CKD and dialysis patients¹⁸. In the current study, the level of

PTH was significantly higher in patients compared to the healthy control group. This study agrees with the results of another study¹⁴. In present study found that phosphorus was significantly higher in patients compared to healthy control group. This study agrees with other studies conducted on HD patients¹⁹. Patients on maintenance hemodialysis frequently have increased serum phosphorus levels²⁰. Protein is an important source of dietary phosphate; however, limiting protein consumption can cause hypoalbuminemia and protein energy wasting²¹.

Sodium imbalances are among the most common electrolyte problems seen in individuals with end-stage renal failure. Because dialysis patients are prone to hyponatremia through numerous routes, assessing extracellular volume (ECV) status is an important initial step in disentangling putative causative variables. Furthermore, several extensive population-based studies have found that low BMI, S. albumin, and S. creatinine levels, and residual renal function degradation are major predictors of hyponatremia in hemodialysis patients²². The present study shows a decrease in serum Na⁺ concentrations between the HD patients and control group. The result is consistent with the study done by Kadhim et al.,²³. Hyperkalemia can be caused by various variables that affect the internal and external potassium balance²⁴.

Among patients with advanced kidney dysfunction, consuming a diet that is high in potassium may result in hyperkalemia. This condition can be further aggravated by frequent use of medications impairing potassium excretion, such as angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers. Additionally, patients with diabetic kidney disease who have hyporeninemic hypoaldosteronism are particularly vulnerable to developing hyperkalemia²⁵. This result is in agreement with a study that found a significant increase in serum K⁺ levels in HD patients compared to control group²⁶. Our results showed no significant difference in Cl⁻ which is consistent with previous research^{26,27}. Our study showed that FGF-23 had a positive significant correlation with (creatinine and urea). The findings of this research are consistent with these results^{2,28,29}. Serum FGF23 levels were linearly associated with PTH, phosphorus, and Ca, ($r = 0.415$, $P < 0.05$), ($r = 0.368$, $P = 0.05$), ($r = 0.233$, $P < 0.05$) respectively, this result is in agreement with the researches findings^{28,30}. There was no-significant association between electrolyte factors (Ca, Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻) and FGF-23.

Conclusions

The FGF23 was higher in patients compared to healthy controls. The results indicate a positive and significant correlation between FGF23 and the clinical parameters (creatinine, urea, PTH, P, and Ca) In addition, our study found no statistically significant correlation to suggest an effect of FGF23 on these parameters (Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻).

References

1. S. Seiler, G. H. Heine, and D. Fliser, "Clinical relevance of FGF-23 in chronic kidney disease," *Kidney Int.*, vol. 76, pp. S34–S42, 2009.
2. M. Raafat, M. Madkour, A. Metwaly, F. M. Nasr, O. Mosbah, and N. El-Sheikh, "Clinical significance of FGF-23 in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients," *Sch. J. Appl. Med. Sci.*, vol. 3, pp. 741–750, 2015.
3. J. A. Johnston, D. R. Nelson, L. Zhang, S. E. Curtis, J. R. Voelker, and J. R. Wetterau, "Estimating the distribution of a novel clinical biomarker (FGF-23) in the US population using findings from a regional research registry," *PLoS One*, vol. 14, no. 6, p. e0218435, 2019.
4. S.-Y. Wang, F. Yang, S. Ma, L.-J. Cui, and R. Zhang, "Role of fibroblast growth factor 23 in patients with chronic kidney disease," *Chin. Med. J. (Engl.)*, vol. 134, no. 04, pp. 404–406, 2021.
5. J. Bacchetta, C. Bardet, and D. Prié, "Physiology of FGF23 and overview of genetic diseases associated with renal phosphate wasting," *Metabolism*, vol. 103, p. 153865, 2020.
6. X. Li, "The FGF metabolic axis," *Front. Med.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 511–530, 2019.
7. G. Coppolino *et al.*, "Iron Infusion and Induced Hypophosphatemia: The Role of Fibroblast Growth Factor-23," *Ther. Apher. Dial.*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 258–264, 2020.
8. L. D. Quarles, "FGF-23 and α -klotho co-dependent and independent functions," *Curr. Opin. Nephrol. Hypertens.*, vol. 28, no. 1, p. 16, 2019.
9. M. L. Mace, E. Gravesen, A. Nordholm, K. Olgaard, and E. Lewin, "Fibroblast growth factor (FGF) 23 regulates the plasma levels of parathyroid hormone in vivo through the FGF receptor in normocalcemia, but not in hypocalcemia," *Calcif. Tissue Int.*, vol. 102, no. 1, pp. 85–92, 2018.
10. J. E. Blau and M. T. Collins, "The PTH-Vitamin D-FGF23 axis," *Rev. Endocr. Metab. Disord.*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 165–174, 2015.
11. B. Lanske and M. S. Razzaque, "Molecular interactions of FGF23 and PTH in phosphate regulation," *Kidney Int.*, vol. 86, no. 6, pp. 1072–1074, 2014.
12. K. Akiyama *et al.*, "Calciprotein particles regulate fibroblast growth factor-23 expression in osteoblasts," *Kidney Int.*, vol. 97, no. 4, pp. 702–712, 2020.
13. M. S. Razzaque, "Does FGF23 toxicity influence the outcome of chronic kidney disease?," *Nephrol. Dial. Transplant.*, vol. 24, no. 1,

- pp. 4–7, 2009.
14. M. H. Shekhany and S. E. Al Mukhtar, “Fibroblast Growth Factor 23 Measurement in the Serum of Patients on Hemodialysis in Erbil Kidney Diseases and Dialysis Department,” *AMJ (Advanced Med. Journal) is Sci. J. Kurdistan High. Counc. Med. Spec.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 79–84, 2018.
 15. G. Jean *et al.*, “High levels of serum fibroblast growth factor (FGF)-23 are associated with increased mortality in long haemodialysis patients,” *Nephrol. Dial. Transplant.*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 2792–2796, 2009.
 16. R. Agoro and K. E. White, “Regulation of FGF23 production and phosphate metabolism by bone–kidney interactions,” *Nat. Rev. Nephrol.*, pp. 1–9, 2023.
 17. M. Rudiansyah *et al.*, “The Correlation between Fibroblast Growth Factor 23 (FGF23) and Iron Profile in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients on Dialysis with Anemia,” *Syst. Rev. Pharm.*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 780–784, 2020.
 18. I. F. Nwosu *et al.*, “Interpretation of Parathyroid Hormone Levels in Renal Impairment,” *Cureus*, vol. 14, no. 6, 2022.
 19. A. G. Mohamed, S. R. Eid, and E. N. Mansour, “OXIDATIVE STRESS OF INTRAVENOUS IRON THERAPY IN HEMODIALYSIS PEDIATRIC PATIENTS,” *AL-AZHAR ASSIUT Med. J.*, vol. 13, no. 4, p. 2, 2015.
 20. J. Serna and C. Bergwitz, “Importance of dietary phosphorus for bone metabolism and healthy aging,” *Nutrients*, vol. 12, no. 10, p. 3001, 2020.
 21. K. Kalantar-Zadeh *et al.*, “Changes in serum albumin and other nutritional markers when using sucroferric oxyhydroxide as phosphate binder among hemodialysis patients: a historical cohort study,” *BMC Nephrol.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2019.
 22. C. M. Rhee, J. C. Ayus, and K. Kalantar-Zadeh, “Hyponatremia in the dialysis population,” *Kidney Int. reports*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 769–780, 2019.
 23. H. M. Kadhim, H. H. Al-Ghanimi, and R. M. Al-Dedah, “Haematological parameters and biochemical indices in patients with chronic kidney disease before haemodialysis Al-Furat Al-Awsat Governorates/Iraq,” in *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2020, vol. 2290, no. 1, p. 20004.
 24. C. I. Ramos, A. González-Ortiz, A. Espinosa-Cuevas, C. M. Avesani, J. J. Carrero, and L. Cuppari, “Does dietary potassium intake associate with hyperkalemia in patients with chronic kidney disease?,” *Nephrol. Dial. Transplant.*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 2049–2057, 2021.
 25. Y. Narasaki *et al.*, “Dietary potassium intake and mortality in a prospective hemodialysis cohort,” *J. Ren. Nutr.*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 411–420, 2021.
 26. W. H. Ajam, “Evaluating of Serum Electrolyte Changes in Chronic Renal Failure Pre and Post Dialysis,” *Medico-legal Updat.*, vol. 20, no. 4, p. 981, 2020.
 27. M. Riasat *et al.*, “Evaluation of trace elements in hemodialysis patients in Pakistan,” *Asian J. Heal. Sci.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. ID48–ID48, 2022.
 28. Y. Nishizawa *et al.*, “Fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23) level is associated with ultrafiltration rate in patients on hemodialysis,” *Heart Vessels*, vol. 36, pp. 414–423, 2021.
 29. H. M. Ahmed and N. T. Younis, “Biochemical Study on Fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23) and its relation with Chronic Kidney Disease,” *Res. J. Pharm. Technol.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 115–118, 2023.
 30. D. Zeng *et al.*, “Correlation of Serum FGF23 and Chronic Kidney Disease-Mineral and Bone Abnormality Markers With Cardiac Structure Changes in Maintenance Hemodialysis Patients,” *Evidence-Based Complement. Altern. Med.*, vol. 2023, 2023.